

Grain yield and net return of rice-based cropping systems under rainfed upland conditions.^a Almora, India, 1985-86.

Crop sequence	Yield (t/ha)				Total cost (\$/ha)		Net return (\$/ha)		Benefit-cost		Protein (t/ha)		Carbohydrate (t/ha)	
	Rainy season		Dry season		OF	IOF	OF	IOF	OF	IOF	OF	IOF	OF	IOF
	OF	IOF	OF	IOF										
Rice - wheat	2.1	2.4	2.5	2.8	377.4	368.4	205.2	290.2	1.5	1.8	0.46	0.50	3.39	3.83
Rice - barley	2.2	2.4	2.2	2.4	373.3	357.8	152.3	215.4	1.4	1.6	0.42	0.46	3.22	3.51
Rice - pea	2.4	2.7	1.9	2.0	337.8	341.8	615.4	682.4	2.8	3.0	0.55	0.59	2.92	3.22
Rice - lentil	2.5	2.7	1.7	1.8	329.5	324.6	527.5	589.1	2.6	2.8	0.60	0.64	2.90	3.10
Rice - rapeseed	2.3	2.5	0.8	1.0	341.6	340.0	207.5	301.7	1.6	1.9	0.33	0.39	1.94	2.16

^a OF = organic fertilizer, IOF = inorganic fertilizer.

12 t farmyard manure (FYM)/ ha. Inorganic fertilizer treatment was recommended NPK for each rainfed crop. Rice received 60-18-25 kg NPK/ ha. All dry season crops grew successfully

(see table). Highest average net return was from rice - pea, followed by rice - lentil; lowest was from rice - barley. Benefit-cost ratios were highest (above 2.0) for rice - legume and lowest for rice - barley. Yields with FYM averaged

0.21 t/ha lower than with inorganic fertilizers. Net return, benefit-cost ratio, and protein and carbohydrate production were higher with inorganic fertilizers. □

Vegetables for high return and water use efficiency in irrigated rice-based systems

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Opportunities for vegetable cultivation on rice fallows are increasing with new facilities for irrigation in coastal Maharashtra (Konkan). Rainfall is high (2,500-3,500 mm) Jun to Sep with a rain-free post-ribe season. We evaluated rice - rice (Ratna), rice - tomato (Sonali), rice - chili (DPL-C-1), and rice - watermelon (Sugarbaby) for gross return and water use.

Soil is lateritic with 1.65% organic C, 2.3 kg available P/ ha, 242 kg available K/ha, and pH 6.0. Wet season rice was entirely rainfed, planted the first week Jul at 20- × 15cm spacing and harvested the second week Oct. Watermelon was planted at 2 × 1 m the first week of Nov, tomato at 60 × 60 cm and chili at 60 × 45 cm were transplanted the first week of Dec, dry season rice was transplanted the second week of Jan. Dry season irrigation was scheduled at 25 mm crop potential evapotranspiration (CPE) for rice, 30

Gross returns of rice - vegetable cropping systems in coastal Maharashtra, India.

Cropping system	Yield (t/ha)		Gross return (\$)			Increase (%)
	Wet season	Dry season ^a	Wet season	Dry season ^b	Total	
Rice - rice	3.7	4.5 (150.0) ^a	711.5	865.3 (5.8)	1576.8	-
Rice - tomato	3.7	49.0 (75.0)	711.5	3769.2 (50.3)	4480.7	184
Rice - chili	3.7	10.0 (115.0)	711.5	3846.2 (33.4)	4557.7	189
Rice - watermelon	3.7	30.0 (30.0)	711.5	2307.7 (76.9)	3019.2	91

^a Figures in parentheses = water use (cm). ^b Figures in parentheses = gross return (\$)/cm water.

for tomato, 36 for chili, and 10 for watermelon. Depth of irrigation per turn was 50 mm for rice, tomato, and chili, and 20 liters/basin for watermelon. Rice received 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha in both seasons; tomato, 150-75-50; chili, 150-50-50; and watermelon, 100-50-50. Protection from pests was need-based.

Increase in gross income was 184% for rice - tomato, 189% for rice - chili, and 91% for rice - watermelon (see table). Gross returns/cm water used was 8 times higher for rice - tomato, 6 times higher for rice - chili, and 13 times higher for rice - watermelon than for rice - rice. □

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